

Project Report On
“STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT FOUR
STOREY APARTMENT BUILDING”

Bharatpur-11, Chitwan

(Course code: CVL 490)

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In the partial fulfillment of requirements for the Bachelor's
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(Course code: CVL 490)

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this study entitled ““**STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT FOUR STOREY APARTMENT BUILDING**” is based on our original work. Related works on the topic by other researchers have been duly acknowledged. We owe all the liabilities relating to the accuracy and authenticity of the data and any other information included hereunder.

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Recommendation

This is to certify that this project work entitled “**STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT FOUR (4) STOREY APARTMENT BUILDING**” prepared and submitted by **Shree Krishna Rimal**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the degree of Bachelor of Engineering (BE) in 4 Years (Civil Engineering) awarded by Pokhara University, has been completed under my/our supervision. I/we recommend the same for acceptance by Pokhara University.

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Date:2024

Departmental Acceptance

The project entitled “**STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT FOUR STOREY APARTMENT BUILDING**” prepared by **Shree Krishna Rimal** in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of bachelor’s in civil engineering has been accepted as a real record of work.

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Date:

Certificate

This project entitled “**STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT FOUR STOREY APARTMENT BUILDING**” prepared and submitted by **Shree Krishna Rimal** has been examined by us and is accepted for the award of the degree of bachelor’s in civil engineering by Pokhara University.

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Abstract

The project is a final year project for a **Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering.** This project aims to increase our understanding and utilize our knowledge in the design and structural analysis of buildings located in Chitwan. This project provides an opportunity to analyze and enhance our skill in the structural design of multistoried apartment buildings, and the design of overall components of buildings (beam, column, slab) using software like ETABS & Auto-cad in detail.

Firstly, preliminary design was prepared for the column, beam, and slab from both moment and deflection criteria, and the dimension of each member was obtained. For the design of columns of square shape and beams of rectangular shape were selected. The size of the column from the preliminary design is found to be 350mm*350mm, and the beam is 230mm*350mm in size.

The Story Displacement, Story Drift, Beam-Column capacity Ratio, and PMM Ratio were also analyzed and checked with the standard limit. Manual vertical load calculation, manual lateral force analysis for each storey level, detailed static analysis using ETABS vs20.0.0. and design of critical slab, beam, column, footing, and staircase, was carried out. Here, the main focus was on structural analysis and design of a multi-storied frame structure. Materials properties were assumed as per the common practice and soil bearing capacity was also assumed as 150 kn/m^2 as per municipal norms. The design of elements was done by using limit state design philosophy which is economical, safe, and reliable. The Analysis and designing tools used in this project is ETABS v 20.0.0. and AUTOCAD was used for detail drawings. Based on the output result, further tabulation and analysis of all the beams and columns is done in the Excel program. During seismic analysis, base shear was calculated and found to be 442.997 and then it was compared with the result obtained from ETABS. Sample critical beam and column were designed manually using IS 456:2000, with maximum reinforcement for the critical beam being 3 - 16 Φ + 2 - 12 Φ and 2 - 16 Φ + 1 - 12 Φ is provided at top and bottom respectively. In a manual design of critical beam section subjected to maximum bending moment of 62.1093 KN-m., and 8mm Φ two legged vertical stirrups @ 100mm c/c is provided up to the distance 2d from each end at the part of splicing or 8mm Φ two legged vertical stirrups @110mm c/c is provided. bottom. While designing the critical column, subjected to a maximum axial load of 746.563KN, 4 - 25 + 4 - 20 ϕ mm longitudinal bars and transverse of 8mm bars at a spacing of 200mm was

evaluated in design but in real life, we use 150mm spacing. Four different column sections C1, C2, C3, and C4 are provided. The thickness of the waist slab in the staircase was 150mm with a 12mm main bar at 150mm c/c provided. The thickness of the slab was 125mm and provided an 8mm rebar diameter at a spacing of 150mm C/C. A strap footing and combined footing were provided with sizes 1.8m*1.8m and 5m*2.55m respectively. So, reinforcement in both ways of 12mm bars was provided at 150 mm and 100mm spacing c/c respectively. Finally, ductile detailing of each member was carried out by using AUTOCAD as per IS: 13920:1993.

CHAPTER:1

INTRODUCTION

The project works on “**STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT FOUR STOREY APARTMENT BUILDING**” is carried out with a motive to structurally design and analyze multi-stored building to make it earthquake resistant and incorporate present methods of building design and analysis in the world with the requirements of the final year project to meet the partial fulfillment of bachelor in Civil Engineering final year project work of Pokhara University (PU). The design and analysis is based on a detailed plan of a proposed RCC building provided by the project supervisor.

Nepal is located in a seismic zone and is prone to earthquakes. We have experienced several earthquakes in the past, the most recent one being the Gorkha Earthquake of April 25, 2015, which measured 7.8 on the Richter scale. For proper analysis and safe design of structures, carries great importance which is the main reason why we propose to perform seismic resistant building design. In the past, earthquake-resistant building concepts were the surplus qualities for the buildings carrying heavy loads but for now, it has become the basic need even for a normal residential building.

1.1 Background

With the changing living style, increasing population, and more pronounced scarcity of land, the demand for multi-story buildings with larger spans and sizes is soaring day by day (BIZOZA, 2014). The studies related to earthquakes demand the structures to be stronger and safer. The earthquake, being an inevitable natural catastrophe, safe design should hold paramount importance as loss of lives and properties is unpleasant because of the worst scenario it can create (Dahal, 2006) .

In such a trend, earthquakes has become one of the natural challenging factors for efficient construction works. It is one of the dominant constraints while designing building in earthquake prone zone like Nepal as Nepal is dominated by Himalayas- the largest, youngest and seismically active mountain range, The existence of Himalayan range with the world’s highest peak is evidence of high tectonics beneath the country (Agrawal & Shrikhande, 2008).So, emphasis on earthquake resistance design is given to minimize seismic impact.

Structural analysis deals with the prediction of performance of a given structure under stipulated loads and other external effects. Structural analysis and design are used to produce a structure capable of resisting all applied loads without failure during its intended life. Structural design with the use of sound knowledge of structural engineering determines the sizes of members like beam, column, rebar arrangements and others.

These structures are subjected to various loads like concentrated loads, uniformly distributed loads uniformly varying loads, random loads, internal or earthquake load and dynamic forces (Agrawal & shrikhande, 2008). The structure transfers its load to the support and ultimately to the ground. While transferring the loads acting on the structure, the members of the structures are subjected to internal forces like axial force, shear force, bending and torsion moments. Structural analysis deals with analyzing these internal forces in the members of the structure (Agrawal & shrikhande, 2008).

Also with the occurrence of the Gorkha Earthquake occurred in 25 thApril,2015 at 11:56:26 NST ,it has added an extra attention in the design of structure .The initial shock, which registered a moment magnitude of 7.8,struck shortly before noon local time(about 06:11 AM Greenwich mean time).Its epicenter was about 21 miles (34 km) east –southeast of Lamjung and 48 miles (77km) northwest of Kathmandu , and its focal point was 9.3 miles (15km) underground killing about 8000 people and more than 6000 structures in Kathmandu were destroyed.(Nepali times blog 10th may 2015).

The earthquake has created awareness among the people about the seismic effect on the structure, its unique loading patterns, bearing capacity of the subsurface and other effects like wind, story drift for the seismic design and analysis of multistoried buildings. (Rafferty 2020).

1.2 Statement of Problem

The major problem that made rise to our project may be summarized as follow:

- Nepal lying on the active seismic zone is highly prone to frequency major and minor earthquakes, so it has become an important task for engineers to consider earthquake in design of a building.
- In addition to this, there has become a great need for a apartment for the people in Bharatpur.

1.3 Objectives

1.3.1 General Objectives

- To achieve a practical knowledge of structural analysis, design, and detailing of structural components using principles of earthquake-resistant design.

1.3.2. Specific Objective

- Understanding of Architectural Layout of Building.
- Detailed structural analysis of the building using ETABS.
- Design of building safety against different load cases, especially to seismic load.

1.4 Scope and Significance of the Project

- Helps to broaden our skills while using design software like; CAD, ETABS, etc
- Helps to learn to deal with practical problems and manage teamwork.
- Gives an idea of the design of multi-storey building that is resistant to seismic load.
- Reference for the upcoming generation of civil engineering faculty.

1.5 Limitations of the Study

The following are the limitations of the project:

- This study covers only the particular proposed area.
- Our project does not include the architectural design of the building.
- The design is fully based on the terms and conditions of NBC and IS codes and other associated codes.
- Our project mainly focuses on the structural analysis and design phase of the building.
- We are adopting the seismic coefficient method for the analysis of the building.
- The bearing capacity of the soil was taken as 150 KN/m^2

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Every engineering design and construction is the outcome of experience and observations. It is necessary to justify the result of the analysis properly concerning the pre-existing standard results. The design and construction should follow the provisions made in the codes of practice. To create this plan, we gathered data from several textbooks, including Building Bylaws, the Internet, past reports on multistory public buildings, the Indian Standard Code, the Nepal National Building Code, Nepal Building Bylaws, etc.

Some Past Studies

Ragy Jose, Restina Mathew, Sandra Devan, Sankeevthana Venu, Mohith YS (2017) [1] analyzed and designed a G+3 Storey commercial building by using ETABS software. In this article, Analysis is carried out by static method and design is done as per IS 456:2000 guidelines. Also, Drawing and Detailing are done using AutoCAD as per SP34. They concluded that both manual work as well as software analysis gives almost the same result. They also suggested using ETABS software which minimizes the time required for analysis and design.

K. Kiran Mai et. al. (2018) [3] analyzed and designed a G+7 Storey residential building by using ETABS software. They have used AutoCAD for drafting the building plan. As the load is more at the bottom when compared to the top floors, there is no need for providing large sizes at the top. Economizing the column by means of column orientation is larger span longer direction will reduce the amount of bending as a result there are of the steel reduced. In this research, they have considered both gravity and lateral (wind and earthquake) loads as per IS 1893-part 2:2002, IS 456:2000. They have applied various suitable methods for data collection and calculation. They concluded that there is a gradual increase in the value of lateral forces from bottom floor to top floor in software analysis.

M. Nasreen Khan- Int J Innov sci, Eng Technol,(2016) analyzed and design a B+G+8 apartment building by using STAAD. Pro2007, software. All the structural components were designed manually and detailed using Auto-Cad 2016. The structural elements like Ramp, shear wall and retaining walls are also provided. They have provided isolated footing, as per soil investigation report. In this research, they have considered both gravity and lateral (wind and earthquake) loads as per IS 1893-part 2:2002, IS 456:2000. The various

difficulties encountered in the design process and the various constraints faced by the structural engineering in designing up to the architectural drawing were also understood.

S. Thakur, TS Thakur, A Bhardwaj (2021) compared the design and analysis over multi-storey G+8 building with STAAD. Pro and ETABS softwares. The basic wind speed for this study was taken as per IS 875(part 3)-2015 and the shear force and bending moment over each of the component of the building was calculated for different combination of loads. This study shows that STAAD.Pro is more flexible when compared to ETABS software in terms of analysis of structure.

2.1 General code of practice:

2.1.1. NBC105:2020 (Nepal National Building Code)

It is the outcome of the revision of the earlier version of NBC 105:1994 Seismic Design of Building in Nepal. It covers the requirements for seismic analysis and design of various building structure to be constructed in the territory of the Federal Republic of Nepal. This code is applicable for all the buildings, low to high rise building, in general. Its development is relatively recently and requires many document to support it. To compensate for its unavailability, the codes frequently refers Indian Standard Codes.IS

2.1.2. IS Codes of Practices

- **IS 875-1987: (Reaffirmed 2003)- Code of Practice for Design Loads (other than Earthquake) for Building and Structures:**

A building has to perform many function satisfactorily. Design may be based on functions and intended use and occupancy. The structural safety of buildings are being covered by this code by the way of laying down minimum design loads which have to assumed for dead loads, live loads, snow loads and other structural loads.

Part 1: Dead Loads:

This part deals with the dead load to be assumed in the design of the building. This code covers the unit weight or mass of the materials and parts and components in the building that apply to the determination of dead load in the design of building.**Part 2: Imposed Loads:**

Imposed loads are the temporary, changeable or dynamic loads acting upon the structures. The magnitude of these loads is typically related to the occupancy of the

space or the building where the load is applied. For example: the imposed load on a school facility will be different from these in a residential building. This part of code deals with the imposed load of the building produced by the intended occupancy or use.

- **IS 456:2000(Reaffirmed 2005) Plain and Reinforced Concrete- Code of Practice:**

This standard deals with the general structural use of plain and reinforced concrete based on Limit State of Design Method. According to this code, plain concrete structures are those where reinforcement if provided is ignored for determination of the strength of the structure. It does not cover the special requirement of structures, such as shells, folded plates, arches, bridges, chimneys, hydraulic structures, earthquake resistant building etc. but allow the use of separate code for those structures in conjunction with this code.

2.1.3. Indian Standard Special Publications (SP):

For the clarification and explanation for the clauses and equations mentioned in Indian Standard Codes, Bureau of Indian Standard has published some special publications including charts and tables for required values like material properties and explaining examples of designs.

2.1.4. SP 16: Design Aids for Reinforced Concrete to IS 456-1978:

This handbook explains the use of formulae mentioned in IS 456 and provides several design charts and interaction diagrams for flexure, deflection control criteria, axial compression, compression with bending and tension with bending for rectangular cross-sections for circular section in case of compression member) which can greatly expedite the design process if done manually. This design aid is particularly useful for the preliminary design.

2.1.5. Textbooks on RCC Design and Earthquake Engineering:

Many available books related to design of reinforced concrete structure and earthquake engineering written by distinguished authors such as Pillai and Menon, SN Sinha and AK Jain are based on the Indian Standard Codes of Practice and provide sufficient theoretical background with illustrative examples. So, for the analysis and design, references from such textbooks are very helpful. Books related to foundation engineering will also be valuable in the design of building foundation. Besides these, other books related to structural mechanics

(Statics and Dynamics) will also be helpful for performing and verifying the analysis output from computer software.

Apart from these references there may require data related to the past earthquake, the earthquake zoning map and soil condition of the site. These data may be obtained from the government authorities and other concerning organizations.

The reports on the same project prepared by the students of previous batches were also an important reference to the project.

2.2 Design philosophy

2.2.1. Working Stress Method

The Working Stress Method is a method of designing reinforced concrete structures that is based on the assumption that the concrete and steel behave in a linear elastic manner. This means that the stresses in the materials are directly proportional to the strains, and that the materials do not exhibit any plastic or brittle behavior.

The WSM is a relatively simple method to use, and it is still widely used in practice today. However, it has some limitations, such as the fact that it does not take into account the nonlinear behavior of concrete and steel.

Assumption of WSM

1. **Plane section remains plane after bending:** This assumption means that the cross-section of a beam does not change shape after it is bent.
2. **Strain compatibility:** This assumption means that the strains in the concrete and steel are equal at any point in the beam.
3. **Linear elastic behavior of concrete and steel:** This assumption means that the stress-strain relationship for concrete and steel is linear up to the point of failure.
4. **Tensile strength of concrete is ignored:** This assumption means that the tensile strength of concrete is considered to be zero.

The WSM is a relatively conservative method of design, which means that it tends to overestimate the stresses in the materials. This can lead to the use of more reinforcement than is actually necessary, which can increase the cost of the structure.

Factors of Safety

The WSM uses factors of safety to ensure that the structure is safe. The factors of safety are applied to the permissible stresses to account for the uncertainty in the material properties and the loading conditions.

The factors of safety used in the WSM are typically as follows:

1. Concrete: 1.5
2. Steel: 1.2

However, the WSM is a simple and easy-to-use method, and it is still widely used in practice today.

Advantage:

- It is a simple and easy-to-use method.
- It is relatively conservative, which means that it tends to overestimate the stresses in the materials.
- It is still widely used in practice today.

Disadvantages:

- It does not take into account the nonlinear behavior of concrete and steel.
- It can lead to the use of more reinforcement than is actually necessary.
- It is not as accurate as other methods of design, such as the Limit State Method.

2.2.2 Ultimate Load Method

The Ultimate Load Method (ULM) is a method of designing reinforced concrete structures that is based on the assumption that the structure will not fail under any combination of loads that is likely to occur during its lifetime.

The ULM takes into account the nonlinear behavior of concrete and steel, which means that the stresses in the materials are not directly proportional to the strains. This makes the ULM more accurate than the Working Stress Method (WSM), which is based on the assumption that the behavior of concrete and steel is linear elastic.

Assumption of ULM

1. Concrete and steel behave in a non-linear elastic manner.
2. The plane section before bending remains plane after bending.
3. There is strain compatibility between steel and concrete.
4. The ultimate load is calculated by multiplying the working load by a load factor.

The ultimate load of the structure is calculated by multiplying the working load by a load factor. The load factor is a number that is greater than 1 and that accounts for the uncertainty in the material properties and the loading conditions.

Factors of Safety

The ULM uses load factors to ensure that the structure is safe. The load factors are applied to the working load to account for the uncertainty in the material properties and the loading conditions.

The load factors used in the ULM are typically as follows:

1. Dead load: 1.2
2. Live load: 1.5
3. Wind load: 1.6
4. Earthquake load: 2.0

The ULM is a more accurate method of designing reinforced concrete structures than the WSM. However, it is also more complex to use. The choice of which method to use depends on the specific project and the level of accuracy required.

Advantages:

- It takes into account the nonlinear behavior of concrete and steel.
- It is more accurate than the WSM.
- It can lead to the use of less reinforcement than is necessary.

Disadvantages:

- It is more complex to use than the WSM.
- It can be more expensive to design a structure using the ULM.

2.2.3. Limit State Method

The Limit Load Method (LSM) is a method of designing reinforced concrete structures that is based on the concept of limit states. A limit state is a condition in which the structure is no longer able to perform its intended function. The LSM ensures that the structure will not reach any limit state under any combination of loads that is likely to occur during its lifetime.

The LSM takes into account the nonlinear behavior of concrete and steel, which means that the stresses in the materials are not directly proportional to the strains. This makes the LSM

more accurate than the Working Stress Method (WSM), which is based on the assumption that the behavior of concrete and steel is linear elastic.

Assumptions of LSM

1. Concrete and steel behave in a non-linear elastic manner.
2. The plane section before bending remains plane after bending.
3. There is strain compatibility between steel and concrete.
4. The limit load is calculated by considering the possibility of failure of the structure.

The limit loads are calculated by considering the possibility of failure of the structure. This means that the limit loads are calculated by considering the maximum stresses that the materials can withstand.

Factors of Safety

The LSM uses load factors and partial safety factors to ensure that the structure is safe. The load factors are applied to the working load to account for the uncertainty in the material properties and the loading conditions. The partial safety factors are applied to the material properties to account for the uncertainty in the material properties.

The load factors and partial safety factors used in the LSM are typically as follows:

1. Dead load: 1.2
2. Live load: 1.5
3. Wind load: 1.6
4. Earthquake load: 2.0
5. Concrete strength: 1.5
6. Steel strength: 1.2

The LSM is a more complex method to use than the WSM, but it is also more accurate. The LSM can lead to the use of less reinforcement than is necessary, which can be more economical in the long run.

Advantages of LSM:

- It takes into account the nonlinear behavior of concrete and steel.
- It is more accurate than the WSM.
- It can lead to the use of less reinforcement than is necessary.
- It is more rational and scientific than the WSM.

Disadvantages of LSM:

- It is more complex to use than the WSM.
- It can be more expensive to design a structure using the LSM.

There are two main types of limit states in structural design:

1. Ultimate/Collapse limit state (ULS):

This is the condition in which the structure is no longer able to carry the loads that are acting on it. This can happen due to the failure of one or more structural members, or due to the overall instability of the structure. This ultimate limit state may correspond to:

- Flexure,
- Compression,
- Shear, and
- Torsion

2. Serviceability limit state (SLS):

This is the condition in which the structure no longer performs its intended function. This can happen due to excessive deflection, cracking, or vibration.

The ULS is the most critical limit state, and it is the one that is most likely to occur. The SLS is less critical than the ULS, but it is still important to ensure that the structure meets the requirements of its intended use.

This ultimate limit state may correspond to:

- Deflections
- Cracking
- Vibration

2.2.4. COMPARISON BETWEEN STRUCTURAL DESIGN PHILOSOPHIES:

In general, the WSM is the simplest and least accurate method. The ULM is more accurate than the WSM, but it is also more complex. The LSM is the most accurate method, but it is also the most complex.

The choice of which method to use depends on the specific project and the level of accuracy required. For simple projects, the WSM may be sufficient. For more complex projects, the ULM or LSM may be necessary.

Among these methods, the Limit State Method is the most widely used in today's world. This design method employs multiple safety factors to ensure that the structure meets the requirements for safety (in terms of strength, stability, and integrity) and serviceability (in terms of stiffness, durability, and so on). These infinite number of partial safety factors involve considerations for failure mechanisms, material properties, and nature of loading and have a sound probabilistic base. In this method, both safety at ultimate loading conditions and serviceability at regular working loads is considered. Structures are designed based on their most critical state and checked for all other limit states. Due to some of these beneficial reasons our project is also based on Limit State Method (LSM).

2.3. Load Cases and Combinations

2.3.1 Load Cases

Different load cases and load combination cases are considered to obtain more critical element stresses in structure in the course of analysis.

There are altogether four load cases considered for the structural analysis and are mentioned as below:

- a. Dead Load
- b. Live Load
- c. Earthquake Load in X-direction
- d. Earthquake Load in Y-direction

Snow load is not considered.

Earthquake load and wind load doesn't occur at the same time. Some earthquake load is greater than wind load, so earthquake load is considered.

2.4. Structural Analysis

2.4.1 Base Shear

According to NBC 105:2020 Base Shear is Defined as “Total design lateral force or shear force due to earthquake at the base of a structure.”

Simply, base shear is the maximum expected lateral force that will occur due to seismic ground acceleration at the base of a structure. It is calculated using the seismic zone, soil material, and building code lateral force equations. Base shear is an important design consideration for all structures in seismically active areas, as it can cause significant damage or even collapse if not properly resisted.

The purpose of base shear is to distribute the lateral forces of an earthquake throughout the height of a structure. This helps to prevent the structure from overturning or collapsing. Base shear is typically applied at the base of a structure, but it can also be distributed to other parts of the structure, such as the roof or the foundation.

The amount of base shear that a structure is subjected to depends on a number of factors, including the seismic zone, the soil material, the building's height, and the building's structural system. Seismic zones are classified according to the likelihood of an earthquake occurring. Soil material can also affect the amount of base shear, as softer soils are more likely to amplify seismic waves. The height of a structure also plays a role, as taller structures are more susceptible to lateral forces. Finally, the structural system of a building can also affect the amount of base shear, as some structural systems are more effective at resisting lateral forces than others.

Base shear is an important design consideration for all structures in seismically active areas. By properly designing for base shear, engineers can help to ensure that structures will remain standing during an earthquake.

According to IS 1893 (Part I): 2016 clause 7.6.1, the Base shear V_B along any principal direction of a building shall be determined by:

$$V_B = A_h * W$$

Where,

A_h = design horizontal acceleration coefficient value

W = Seismic Weight of Building

2.4.2 Center of mass

According to NBC 105:2020, Center of mass is defined as “The point in a floor through which the resultant of the mass passes.”

Simply, the center of mass (CM) of a structure is the point where the entire mass of the structure is assumed to be concentrated. In seismic analysis, the center of mass is used to determine the location of the inertia forces that are generated during an earthquake. These inertia forces are proportional to the mass of the structure and the acceleration of the ground. The location of the center of mass is important because it affects the distribution of the inertia forces throughout the structure.

If the center of mass is located near the base of the structure, the inertia forces will be concentrated near the base. This can lead to large bending moments and shear forces in the columns and foundation. On the other hand, if the center of mass is located near the top of the structure, the inertia forces will be concentrated near the top. This can lead to large bending moments and shear forces in the beams and slabs.

In general, it is desirable to have the center of mass located as low as possible in a structure. This is because it will help to distribute the inertia forces more evenly throughout the structure and reduce the risk of damage during an earthquake.

Here are some of the factors that can affect the location of the center of mass in a structure:

1. The distribution of mass throughout the structure.
2. The shape of the structure.
3. The location of the lateral load resisting system.

The center of mass can be determined using a variety of methods, including:

1. Analytical methods.
2. Graphical methods.
3. Computer-aided methods.

The method that is used to determine the center of mass will depend on the complexity of the structure and the accuracy that is required. By calculating the static moments around a point or set of reference lines, the center of mass can be found.

$$X_m = \frac{\sum W_i L_i}{\sum W_i}$$

$$Y_m = \frac{\sum W_i B_i}{\sum W_i}$$

Where,

$$\sum W = W (R) + W (N) + W (S) + W \epsilon$$

2.4.3 Center of Stiffness / Rigidity (CR)

According to NBC 105:2020, Center of stiffness or rigidity is defined as “the point in a floor at which the resultants of the resisting forces in the two orthogonal directions intersect.”

The center of rigidity is the point in a structure where all the stiffness of the structure is

concentrated. It is the point where, if a lateral load is applied, the structure will deflect the least. The center of rigidity is also known as the center of stiffness or the center of resistance. The center of rigidity is calculated by taking the weighted average of the positions of all the rigid elements in the structure. The weights are determined by the stiffness of each element. For example, a column that is twice as stiff as a beam will have twice the weight in the calculation of the center of rigidity.

The center of rigidity is an important concept in structural engineering because it can be used to determine the distribution of lateral loads in a structure. If the center of rigidity is not located at the center of mass of the structure, then the lateral loads will cause the structure to rotate. This can lead to the structure becoming unstable.

In a beam, the center of rigidity is located at the centroid of the beam's cross-section. This is because the stiffness of a beam is proportional to the area of its cross-section. In a frame, the center of rigidity is located at the intersection of the centerlines of the most rigid members. The center of rigidity is an important concept to understand for anyone who is involved in the design or analysis of structures. It can help to ensure that structures are designed to be stable and to resist lateral loads.

Figure 1: Center of Mass and Center of Stiffness/Rigidity

2.4.4 Storey Drift

Storey drift is the relative lateral displacement between two consecutive stories of a structure. It is a measure of the flexibility of a structure and its ability to withstand lateral loads, such as wind and earthquakes.

Story drift is calculated by dividing the lateral displacement of one story by the height of that story. The resulting value is typically expressed as a percentage or a ratio. For example, a story drift of 0.02 would mean that the lateral displacement of one story is 2% of the height of that story.

The calculation of story drift is relatively straight for apartment. However, the specific method used to calculate story drift can vary depending on the structural analysis software being used. In general, the following steps are involved in calculating story drift:

- ❖ The lateral displacements of each story are calculated using a structural analysis software.
- ❖ The story heights are determined.
- ❖ The story drift is calculated by dividing the lateral displacement of each story by the height of that story.

The story drift limits for a structure are typically specified in the building code for the area where the structure is located. These limits are based on the seismic hazard of the area and the type of structure. For example, a structure in a high-seismic area will have lower story drift limits than a structure in a low-seismic area.

2.4.5 Torsion

Torsion is a twisting moment that can be applied to a structure. It is caused by lateral loads that are not evenly distributed across the plan of a structure. Torsion can cause significant damage to a structure, especially in seismically active areas.

In IS code, torsional irregularity is defined as a condition in which the plan of a structure is not symmetrical and the distribution of lateral loads is not uniform. Torsional irregularity can be caused by a number of factors, including the shape of the structure, the location of openings, and the presence of cantilevers.

There are two types of torsional irregularity:

1. Plan irregularity:

This type of irregularity is caused by asymmetries in the plan of a structure. For example, a building with a T-shaped plan would be considered torsionally irregular.

2. Elevation irregularity:

This type of irregularity is caused by asymmetries in the elevation of a structure. For example, a building with a sloping roof would be considered torsionally irregular.

Torsional irregularity can increase the seismic demand on a structure. This is because torsion can cause the structure to twist, which can lead to shear failures and damage to the structural elements.

Figure 2 :torsion

2.4.4 Accidental Eccentricity

Accidental eccentricity in an apartment building is a critical concept in structural engineering that can have significant implications for the safety and stability of the building. Eccentricity, in this context, refers to the misalignment between the center of mass (or center of gravity) of the building and its center of stiffness (or center of resistance). This misalignment can lead to uneven distribution of forces within the structure, especially during dynamic events such as earthquakes or strong winds, potentially causing torsion or twisting in the building within the structure, especially during dynamic events such as earthquakes or strong winds, potentially causing torsion or twisting in the building.

2.5 Soft Ware

In the past, construction and civil engineering projects were designed and built using manual methods. This involved a lot of paperwork, calculations, and drawings. The process was time-consuming and error-prone.

With the arrival of software in the construction and civil engineering industry has undergone a major transformation. Software applications are now used to design, analyze, and simulate projects. This has led to a significant increase in efficiency and accuracy.

For example, software can be used to create 3D models of projects. This allows engineers to visualize the project and to identify potential problems. Software can also be used to

perform complex calculations and to simulate the behavior of projects under different conditions. This helps engineers to ensure that projects are safe and reliable.

The use of software has revolutionized the construction and civil engineering industry. It has made projects more efficient, accurate, and safe. As a result, different Civil Engineering Software is now an essential tool for civil engineers.

Civil engineering software is a broad term that encompasses a wide variety of software applications used by civil engineers in their work. These applications can be used for a variety of tasks, including:

1. Drafting and design:

Civil engineering software can be used to create 2D and 3D drawings of civil engineering projects. This includes roads, bridges, buildings, and other structures.

2. Analysis:

Civil engineering software can be used to analyze the behavior of civil engineering structures under different loads. This includes static loads, dynamic loads, and environmental loads.

3. Simulation:

Civil engineering software can be used to simulate the performance of civil engineering structures under different conditions. This can be used to test the safety and reliability of structures before they are built.

4. Project management:

Civil engineering software can be used to manage civil engineering projects. This includes tracking costs, schedules, and resources.

Some of the most popular civil engineering software applications include:

2.5.1 AutoCAD/ AutoCAD Civil 3D:

AutoCAD is a computer-aided design (CAD) software application that is used by civil engineers to create 2D and 3D drawings of civil engineering projects. It is a powerful tool that can be used to create a wide variety of drawings, including plans, elevations, sections, and details.

In civil engineering, AutoCAD is used for a variety of tasks, including:

1. Planning and design:

AutoCAD can be used to create plans, elevations, and sections of civil engineering projects. This allows civil engineers to visualize their projects and to make sure that they are safe and efficient. For example, AutoCAD can be used to create plans for a new road or bridge, or to design a new building.

2. Drafting:

AutoCAD can be used to create detailed drawings of civil engineering projects. These drawings can be used to communicate the design of the project to contractors and other Clients. For example, AutoCAD can be used to create detailed drawings of a new building's foundation, or to create a set of as-built drawings for a road project.

3. 3D modeling:

AutoCAD can be used to create 3D models of civil engineering projects. This allows civil engineers to visualize their projects in three dimensions and to analyze the behavior of their projects under different loading conditions. For example, AutoCAD can be used to create a 3D model of a new bridge to analyze its strength and stability.

4. Documentation:

AutoCAD can be used to create documentation for civil engineering projects. This documentation can include plans, elevations, sections, and details. For example, AutoCAD can be used to create a set of construction drawings for a new building.

Overall, AutoCAD is a powerful and versatile software application that can be used for a variety of tasks in civil engineering. It is a valuable tool for civil engineers who are involved in the design, drafting, and documentation of civil engineering projects.

2.5.2 ETABS:

ETABS is a structural analysis and design software application that was first released in 1977 by Computers and Structures, Inc. (CSI). It is a powerful tool that can be used to analyze a wide variety of structures, including buildings, bridges, and offshore platforms.

ETABS is based on the finite element method, which is a numerical method for solving problems in structural mechanics. The finite element method breaks down a structure into a

series of small elements and then analyzes the behavior of each element. The results of the analysis are then used to determine the overall behavior of the structure.

ETABS can be used to perform a variety of tasks, including:

1. Static analysis:

This is the most common type of analysis performed in ETABS. It is used to analyze structures that are subjected to static loads, such as gravity loads, wind loads, and earthquake loads.

2. Dynamic analysis:

This type of analysis is used to analyze structures that are subjected to dynamic loads, such as earthquake loads and impact loads. Dynamic analysis can be performed using either linear or nonlinear methods.

3. Seismic analysis:

ETABS can be used to perform seismic analysis of structures. This involves analyzing the behavior of structures under earthquake loads.

4. Design:

ETABS can be used to design structures. This involves specifying the materials and dimensions of the members of the structure to ensure that the structure is safe and meets the design criteria.

ETABS is a versatile software application that can be used for a variety of tasks. It is a valuable tool for civil engineers who are involved in the design and analysis of structures.

CHAPTER3
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Figure 3 : Flow Diagram of Research Methodology

3.1 PLANNING

The process of developing a detailed scheme or strategy for a specific purpose. In the context of a final year project on an apartment building, planning would involve identifying the project & goals, objectives, and scope; developing a timeline and budget; and identifying and scheduling the necessary tasks and resources.

3.2. FUNCTIONAL PLANNING

Functional planning is the process of determining the purpose of a civil engineering project and how it will meet the needs of its users. This includes identifying the functional requirements of the project, such as the size, layout, orientation and features of the project.

3.3. COLLECTION OF DATA

The collection of data is an important step in starting the project on designing an apartment building. The data can be collected through a variety of methods, such as surveys, interviews, and site visits. Once the data has been collected, it needs to be analyzed to identify the key requirements for the building. The analysis of the data will help to ensure that the building is designed in a way that meets the needs of its users and is secure.

3.4. ARCHITECTURAL DRAWING

These drawings provide a visual representation of the building design and layout. On the basis of Architectural drawing further analysis of building is done. The architectural drawings for an apartment building typically include site plan, building plan, and detail architectural design of building including elevation, reinforcement detailing etc. Furthermore, the architectural design of the apartment building is done strictly on the basis of NBC 106:2015 “ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN REQUIREMENTS”.

3.5. STRUCTURAL PLANNING

Structural planning is the process of designing the structural system for a building. This includes the type of framing system, the size of the beams and columns, and the type of foundation. The structural system is designed to withstand the loads that the building will be subjected to, such as the weight of the building itself, the weight of the people and equipment that will be using the building, and the weight of any environmental loads, such as wind and snow. In the design of a apartment building, the structural planning process is especially important because these buildings need to be able to withstand a lot of weight

and traffic. The structural system must be designed to be safe and secure, and it must also be able to accommodate the future needs of the building.

3.6. LOAD ASSESSMENT AND PRELIMINARY DESIGN

Preliminary Design of structural member is based on the IS Code provisions for beam, column, slab of serviceability criteria for deflection control and moment criteria method. Appropriate sizing is done with consideration to the fact that the preliminary design based on gravity loads is required to resist the lateral loads acting on the structure. The details of preliminary design computations for slabs, beams and columns are prepared.

3.7. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

Modeling and analysis of the structure is done by using ETABS software. The Modeling and analysis is done being based of NBC 105:2020 “SEISMIC DESIGN OF BUILDINGS IN NEPAL”. This can be done by creating a computer model of the building and then applying loads to the model.

3.8. REINFORCEMENT DETAILING AND DRAWING

After completion of the structural analysis and design, the reinforcement detailing of various structural component is done as per the codal provision of IS 13920-2016, with some suitable modifications whenever necessary. This code includes the common method of detailing of reinforcement based on good practice with deviations made in special cases to comply with IS 456:2000. For the purpose drawing and drafting we will gone use the well-known drafting software AutoCAD 2024.

Chapter 4

PRELIMINARY DESIGN

Preliminary design results serve as basic dimensions to be used during the initial modeling of the building in structural analysis software. These dimensions can then be adjusted based on the structural response parameters obtained. During this analysis, the most critical location of each element is identified and its dimensions are calculated using IS 456:2000.

4.1 load calculation

The gravity loads on the structural elements are taken as per IS 875 Part I (dead loads) and IS 875 Part II (imposed loads). The unit weights of materials taken for the calculation of the dead load of the structure are as follows.

Table 1: Unit Weight of Materials used (source IS 875 Part1)

S.N.	Material Used	Unit Weight	Type of Member
1.	Cement Concrete for RCC	25 KN/m ³	Beams, Columns, Slabs
2.	Common Brunt Clay Brick Masonry	19.2 KN/m ³	Infill & Partition Walls
3.	Motor Screed on floor	20 KN/m ³	All Flooring Spaces
4.	Ceiling Plaster	20KN/m ³	Ceiling
5.	Floor Finish	0.22KN/m ³	Floor

4.2 Preliminary design of RCC Slab

The preliminary design of the RCC slab for the floor and roof of the proposed building is based on fulfillment of deflection control criteria of IS 456:2000 and the behavior of the floor slab as a rigid diaphragm in earthquake resistant design based on IS 1893:2016.

The project building has largest span of 4.650m*3.275m.

$l_x = 3275\text{mm}$ (i.e. the smallest of the two dimensions of the slab)

$l_y = 4650\text{mm}$ (i.e. the largest of the two dimensions of the slab)

$$\frac{l_y}{l_x} = \frac{4650}{3275} = 1.41 < 2$$

Hence the slab is two-way continuous slab.

From IS 456:2000 Clause 23.2

Control of Deflection, we can draw out the following methodical steps to get the thickness of slab. Here d represents the thickness of the slab

$$\frac{\text{span}(l)}{\text{effective depth}(d)} \leq abgd$$

Here, $l = l_x = 4317\text{mm}$

$a = 32$ (Ref. IS 456: 2000 Cl. 24.1 Note2) (For continuous slab)

$b = \text{span factor} = 1$ for largest span less than 10m (Ref. IS 456: 2000 Cl. 23.2.1 b.)

Assuming Fe415 rebar and

Assuming 1% reinforcement and $f_s = 0.58 \cdot 415 = 240 \text{ N/mm}^2$

From Fig. 4, (Page 38) IS 456: 2000

$g = 1$

$d = 1$ no compression reinforcement in the slab (Ref. IS 456: 2000 Cl. 23.2.1 d)

$l = 1$ for slab being rectangular section without flange (Ref. IS 456: 2000 Cl. 23.2.1 e)

$$d_{\text{eff}} = \frac{3275}{1 \cdot 1 \cdot 1 \cdot 32} = 102.34\text{mm}$$

Take the overall depth (D) as 120 mm

A clear cover of 15mm for main bar of diameter 10mm we get the effective depth of slab as:

Effective Depth of Slab (d_{eff}) = Overall Depth - 0.5x Dia. of main bar - Clear Cover

$$= D - \frac{\phi}{2} - \text{clear cover}$$

$$= 120 - 0.5 \times 10 - 15(\phi)$$

can be either 10 mm or 8 mm not more or less)

$$d_{\text{eff}} = 100\text{mm} < 102.34\text{mm (OK)}$$

4.3 Preliminary design of RCC Beam

GROUND FLOOR

From the architectural plan of the proposed building, the maximum span length of the beam is **7.317m** c/c at BC-4.

Maximum span 7.317m c/c at BC-4 is taken. Preliminary Design can be done either by

- 1) Deflection Control Criteria
- 2) By Moment Criteria

4.3.1 Design by deflection control criteria

The methodical steps in designing the beam element preliminarily with respect to IS 456:2000, IS 1893, IS13920, IS 4326 are same as the slab element. From **Clause 23.2IS 456:2000** we can draw out the following methodical steps to get minimum depth of beam;

$$\frac{\text{span}(l)}{\text{effectivedepth}(d)} \leq abgd$$

Where,

Span (l) = 4.650m = 4650mm (i.e. the largest available span length from the floor plan.)

a = 26 (for continuous beam) (Ref. IS 456: 2000 Cl. 23.2.1)

b = span factor = 1 for largest span less than 10m (Ref. IS 456: 2000 Cl. 23.2.1)

Assuming 1 % tension reinforcement and $f_s = 240 \text{ N/mm}^2$

From **Fig. 4, (Page 38) IS 456: 2000**

$$g = 1$$

Assume 0 % compression reinforcement (**Fig. 5, (Page 39) IS 456: 2000**)

$$d = 1 \quad \text{(Ref. IS 456: 2000 Cl. 23.2.1 d)}$$

$l = 1$ for slab being rectangular section without flange (**Ref. IS 456: 2000 Cl. 23.2.1 e**)

$$d_{\text{eff}} = \frac{4650}{26 \cdot 1 \cdot 1 \cdot 1 \cdot 1} = 178.846 \text{ mm} \approx 220 \text{ mm}$$

Thus the effective depth is 220 mm

A minimum clear cover of 25mm is taken for main bar of diameter 16 mm, then we get the overall depth of beam as:

Overall Depth of Beam (D) = Effective Depth + 0.5x Dia. of main bar + Clear Cover

$$= 220 + 0.5 \times 16 + 25$$

$$= 253 \text{ mm}$$

Therefore take $D = 300 \text{ mm}$

$$\frac{D}{b} = (1.5 \text{ to } 2)$$

$$\frac{D}{b} = 1.5$$

Therefore $b = \frac{300}{1.5} = 200 \text{ mm}$

$$D = 300 \text{ mm}$$

$b = 200 \text{ mm}$ (The width of the member shall not be less than 200mm) (**IS13920, clause no. 6.1.3**)

4.3.2 Determination of depth of beam by moment criteria

Area of Influence = 10.190m² (From architectural drawing)

Load Calculations:

Dead Load of Slab = 25*0.125*10.190 =31.843KN

DL of screed with punning 25 mm thick (DL_{screed}) = 21*.025*10.190 =5.349KN

(Ref : For g, IS 875 Part I Table II Page 8)

DL of marble 25 mm thick (DL_m) = 22* .025*10.190= 5.604KN

(Ref : For g, IS 875 Part I Table II Page 8)

Dead Load of Beam = 25*0.3*0.2*4.65 =6.975 KN

Live Load (LL) =3 KN/m² (Ref. 875 Part II)

LL on influence area= 3*10.190= 30.57KN

Wall Load = unit weight*(% opening)* wall thickness (10")* floor height.

19.2*0.7*4.650*0.23*2.6 = 37.085 KN

Total Load = Sum of above loads = 117.426 KN

Factored Load= 1.5* Total Load

$$= 1.5* 117.256$$

$$= 176.139 \text{ KN}$$

$$W_U = \frac{176.139}{4.650} = 37.879 \text{ KN/m}$$

Max Moment (Mu) = $\frac{wl*l}{12} = \frac{45.02*4.65*4.65}{12} = 68.25\text{KN-m}$ (Both end fixed with UDL)

$$\text{Moment of Resistance (Mu)} = 0.149 f_{ck} * b * d^2 \text{ for Fe250}$$

$$0.138 f_{ck} * b * d^2 \text{ for Fe415}$$

$$0.133 f_{ck} * b * d^2 \text{ for Fe500}$$

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{68.25 * 10^6}{0.138 * 20 * 200}}$$

$$\text{Thus } d_{\text{eff}} = 351.626 \text{ mm} \approx 380 \text{ mm}$$

Overall Depth of Slab (D) = Effective Depth + 0.5x Dia. of main bar + Clear Cover

$$= d_{\text{eff}} + \frac{\phi}{2} + \text{clear cover}$$

$$= 380 + 0.5 \times 16 + 25 (\phi \text{ is taken } 16 \text{ mm})$$

$$D = 413 \text{ mm Adopt } D = 450 \text{ mm (27")}$$

$$B = D/1.5 = 300 \text{ mm Adopt } B = 300 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Adopted Size of Beam} = (230 \times 350) \text{ mm}^2$$

4.4 Preliminary design of RCC column

In our plan elevation, we choose C4 column which has maximum influence area of 14.804 m² excluding the area of column. It is the intermediate column and carries maximum axial load. The column of bottom floor is designed and it has maximum size than above all. It contains maximum percentage of steel reinforcement. We have considered maximum 3% of steel reinforcement. We consider M25 grade mix and Fe500 bars in the column. Assume initial size as 300*300 mm²

Load Calculation:

$$\text{Dead Load of Slab} = 25 * 0.125 * 14.804 = 44.412 \text{ KN}$$

$$\text{D.L. of the screed with punning} = 14.804 * 0.025 * 21 = 7.772 \text{ KN}$$

(Ref : For g IS 875 Part I Table II Page 8)

D.L. of Floor finish of marble = $14.804 \times 0.025 \times 22 = 8.142$ KN

(Ref : For g IS 875 Part I Table II Page 8)

Dead Load of Beam = unit wt*B*D*(length of half portion of the beam)

$25 \times 0.3 \times 0.45 \times (4.542 + 3.082) = 25.731$ KN

Live Load (LL) = 3 KN/m²

LL on influence area = $3 \times 14.804 = 44.412$ KN

Dead load of column = $25 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 \times 3 = 18.75$ KN

Wall load = percentage of wall* unit wt* wall thickness* floor height* (length of half portion of the wall)

$19.2 \times 0.7 \times (4.542 + 3.082) \times 0.23 \times 2.6 = 63.160$ KN

Total Load = Sum of above loads = 212.379 KN

Factored Load = $1.5 \times$ Total Load

$$= 1.5 \times 212.379$$

$$= 318.568 \text{ KN}$$

Factored Load = 318.568 KN per floor for critical column

Total Factored load to be bore by our designed column = $4 \times 318.568 = 1274.274$ KN

For axially loaded short column (From Code IS456:2000 Cl 39.3)

$$P_u = 0.4f_{ck} \times A_c + 0.67 \times f_y \times A_{st}$$

$$1274.274 \times 1000 = 0.4 \times 25 \times 0.97 \times A_g + 0.67 \times 500 \times 0.03 \times A_g \quad (\% \text{steel})$$

$$= 3\%, f_{ck} = 25 \text{MPa}, f_y = 500 \text{KN/m}^2$$

Solving for A_g ,

$$A_g = 64520.202 \text{ mm}^2$$

For square column, $D = (A_g)^{0.5} = 254 \text{ mm}$

Hence, adopting a 350mm x 350mm column size.

Chapter 5

DESIGN PROCEDURE OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENT

5.1 Slab Design:

Slab panels are to be designed for the limit state of bending moment and deflection. The thickness of slab is governed by deflection, the steel area at mid span are provided at the bottom and at support sections steel section are provided at the top due to the nature of bending moments. The slab is designed for 1m wide strips. The design steps of slab are as follow:

1. Clear size, L_x and L_y .
2. Effective depth is taken from preliminary design
3. Calculation of effective span:

$$l_x = L_x + d \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

(Less of the above two values are taken.)

4. Calculation of the load (Dead load and Live load)
5. If $\frac{L_y}{L_x} = 2$, Two-way slab is designed.
6. Calculation of bending moments:

Positive and according to $\frac{L_y}{L_x}$ moments (α_x and α_y) are taken from **IS: 456-2000, Table 26**, $\frac{L_y}{L_x}$ ratio.

Calculate Bending moment as **(Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 24.4.1)**

$$M_x = \alpha_x * W * l_x^2 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$M_y = \alpha_y * W * l_x^2 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where, M_x and M_y are the moments on the strips of unit width spanning l_x and l_y respectively.

α_x and α_y are bending moment coefficients, l_x and l_y are the length of short and long span respectively.

7. Effective depth from moment criteria is calculated using following formula:

$$\text{For Fe 500, } M_{\max} = 0.133 f_{ck} b d^2 \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

8. Area of steel required for negative moment at continuous edge and positive moment at mid span: **(Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 38.1 G-1.1)**

For short span, it is calculated using following formula,

$$M_x = 0.87 f_y A_{stx} d \left\{ 1 - \frac{f_y A_{stx}}{d b f_{ck}} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

For long span, it is calculated using following formula,

$$M_y = 0.87 f_y A_{sty} d \left\{ 1 - \frac{f_y A_{sty}}{d b f_{ck}} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

9. Check for minimum steel from codes:

For Fe 500, Minimum area of steel = 0.12% of bD

10. Maximum spacing:

$$\text{Spacing} \leq 3d$$

$$\leq 300\text{mm}$$

11. Minimum area of steel required is provided in edge strip.

12. Corner steels (torsion steel):

Area of each layer of steel at corners = 75% of area required for maximum mid span moment

13. Shear is checked at the edge of short span. **(Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 40.1)**

$$v_u = \frac{V}{2} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

$$\tau_v = \frac{V}{bd_1} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Percentage of steel, $p = (A_{sty}/2)/bd_1$

For p & M20 grade concrete, τ_c is taken from IS 456:2000 Table 19 p.73 and k is taken as per IS 456:2000, Cl.40.2.1.1, p.72.

$$\tau'_c = k\tau_c > \tau_v \quad \text{O.K.}$$

14. Development Length is checked at both short and long edge. **(Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl.26.2)**

$$L_d \leq (1.3M_1/V) + L_o \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

$$\frac{M_{bd}}{4Tbd} \geq \frac{M}{V} + LLD \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

15. Deflection is checked at mid span of short span according to **IS 456:2000, Cl.23.2.1, p.37:**

$$\frac{M}{d} \leq \alpha\beta\gamma\delta\lambda \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

5.2 Column Design:

Column are vertical structural members that support the beam and slab and transfer the load to the foundation. The design of column section can be made by the limit state method. Column in frame structures under seismic load are generally biaxially loaded and hence design accordingly. The design procedure of column is given below:

1. Size of column for preliminary design
2. If slenderness ratio = (le/LLD) < 12, Case: Short column

(Where, LLD = least lateral dimension)

3. Check for eccentricity (Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 25.4)

$$e_{min} = L/500 + D/30 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Therefore, Moment due to eccentricity = $P_u \times e_{min}$

Reinforcement is equally distributed on four sides

4. Axial force (P_u), moments (M_{ux} & M_{uy}) are taken from ETABS analysis.
5. Assume percentage of reinforcement (p), and carried out trial for this percentage.
6. Find p/f_{ck} , d/D and $p_u/f_{ck}bd$
7. Find ($M_u/f_{ck}bD^2$) from chart as per the value obtain from step 6 from **SP-16**.
8. Calculation of P_{uz} (**Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 39.6**)

$$P_{uz} = 0.446f_{ck}A_c + 0.75f_y * A_{sc} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

A_c = Area of concrete

A_{sc} = Area of steel

9. Find (p_u/p_{uz}) , (M_{uy}/M_{uy1}) , (M_{uz}/M_{uz1}) and (α_n)
10. Find $(M_{uy}/M_{uy1})^{\alpha_n} + (M_{uz}/M_{uz1})^{\alpha_n}$
11. If $(M_{uy}/M_{uy1})^{\alpha_n} + (M_{uz}/M_{uz1})^{\alpha_n} < 1.0$, Then O.K., if not, go to step 5.
12. Design of diameter and pitch of lateral ties:

- The diameter of lateral ties should not be less than one fourth diameter of largest longitudinal bar

$$\Phi_T \geq \phi/4$$

$$\geq 6\text{mm}$$

- Pitch of ties:

Pitch of ties \leq least lateral dimension

$$\leq 16*L$$

$$\leq 300\text{mm}$$

13. Check for ductility criteria

- The spacing of hoops shall not exceed half the LLD of column.
- Special confining reinforcement shall be provided over a length l_0 from each joint face $>$ LLD

$>1/6$ of clear span of member

>450 mm

- Lap splices shall be provided only in the central half of the member
- Hoops shall be provided over the entire splices spacing of which should be less than 150mm c/c at splices.

5.3 Beam Design:

Design of beam requires determination of the cross-sectional dimensions and reinforcement details to satisfy both serviceability and strength requirements. In beams, spacing of

reinforcement bar are small and governed by minimum spacing requirement than maximum spacing for crack control. The reinforcements are provided to satisfy strength requirements. Beams are designed for that worst condition. So, the maximum values from the combination have been used for the design. The size of beam is known through preliminary design and is designed as doubly reinforced section to meet the criteria of **IS 13920:1993 Cl. 6.2.1**. The design procedure of beam is given below:

1. Size of the beam from preliminary design
2. Factored bending moment (M_u) and factored shear force (V_u) from ETABS analysis
3. Assuming diameter of reinforcement bars, with 30 mm clear cover, effective depth is calculated as

$$d = D - (\phi/2) - cc$$

..... (1)

Where,

D = Overall depth of beam

ϕ = Dia. of bar

cc = clear cover

Determination of limiting bending moment (**Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 38.1 G-1.1**)

$$M_{lim} = 0.36 * f_{ck} * b * X_m (d - 0.4 X_m)$$

..... (2)

If $M_u > M_{lim}$, doubly reinforced section is designed

If $M_u < M_{lim}$, singly reinforced section is designed

Where,

f_{ck} = Characteristic Compressive Strength of Concrete

B = Width of beam

X_m = maximum depth of neutral axis

d = Effective depth of neutral axis

4. Area of tension steel required for M_{lim} (Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 38.1 G-1.1)

$$M_{lim} = 0.87 \cdot f_y \cdot A_{st1} \cdot (d - (f_y \cdot A_{st1}) / (f_{ck} \cdot b)) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where,

A_{st1} = Area of steel in Tension

F_y = Characteristics strength of steel

5. Area of tension steel required for additional bending moment (M_u - M_{lim}) (Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 38.1 G-1.2)

$$M_u - M_{lim} = (f_{sc} - f_{cc}) A_{sc} (d - d') \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where, f_{sc} is stress in steel in compression

For $\frac{d'}{d}$ is taken from SP-16, Table F, p.13

And f_{cc} = 0.446f_c

Area of compression steel required for additional bending moment M_u

- M_{lim} is calculated as

$$(f_{sc} - f_{cc}) \cdot A_{sc} = 0.87 \cdot f_y \cdot A_{st2} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$A_{st} = A_{st1} + A_{st2} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

6. Check for minimum area of tension steel (Ref. IS 456:2000, Cl.26.5.1.1 (a), p.46-47)

$$A_o/bd = 0.85/f_y \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Where,

A_o = area of tension steel

A_{st} = Area of steel

7. Check for maximum area of tension steel (**Ref. IS 456:2000, Cl.26.5.1.1 (a), p. 47**)

$$A_o = 0.04bD \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

8. Check for shear

Permissible shear stress τ_c is taken from **IS 456:2000, Table 19, p.73** for designed p_t .

Nominal Shear stress,

$$\tau_v = \frac{V_u}{bd} \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

$\tau_{c,max}$ is taken from **IS 456:2000, Table 20, p.73** for designed grade of concrete. If

$$\tau_c \leq \tau_v \leq \tau_{c, max}$$

Design shear force,

$$V_{us} = V_u - \tau_c bd \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

$$V_{us} = (0.87f_y * A_{sv} * d) / x \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

Area and spacing of the stirrups are taken considering, spacing $x < 0.75d$ and $< 300\text{mm}$

9. Check for ductility

Percentage of minimum and maximum area of tension reinforcements according to **IS 13920:1993**,

$$\rho_{\min} = (0.24 \sqrt{f_{ck}}) / f_y \quad \dots (12)$$

$$\rho_{\max} = 2.5\%$$

f_y = yield stress of steel

10. Ductility check for shear

Spacing $x \leq d/4$

$$\leq 8 \phi \quad \geq 100 \text{ mm}$$

5.4 Staircase:

The staircase is a stepped longitudinal structural system for the moment from one floor to another floor. The shape and structural arrangement of staircase depends up on types of construction and availability of stair. There should be equal rise and tread for every parallel step.

The design procedures of staircase are as follows:

1. Assume thickness of waist slab
2. Calculation of load
3. Calculation of reactions
4. Calculation of maximum bending moment

B.M._{max} = at distance X where shear force is zero.

5. Calculation of area of steel (**Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 38.1 G-1.1**)

$$M = 0.87 * f_y * A_{st} (d - (f_y * A_{st} / f_{ck} * b)) \quad \dots (1)$$

6. Check for shear (**Ref. IS 456:2000 Cl. 40.1**)

Percentage of steel,

$$p = (A_{sty} / 2) / bd_1 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

For p & M20 grade concrete, τ_c is taken from IS 456:2000, table 19 p.73 and k are taken as per IS 456:2000, Cl.40.2.1, p.72.

Therefore, $\tau'_c = k\tau_c > \tau_v$ O.K.

5.5 Foundation:

Foundations are the structural elements that transfer loads from the buildings or individual columns to the earth. If these loads are to be properly transmitted, foundations must be designed to prevent excessive settlement or rotation, to minimize differential settlement and to provide adequate safety against sliding and overturning. There is various type of foundations. Some of them are:

- i. Isolated footings
- ii. Strip foundation and wall footings
- iii. Combined footings
- iv. Raft or mat foundation
- v. Pile foundation

The base reaction and the biaxial moment are obtained for the ETABS20.0 which are used to design the individual footing. The design procedure of foundation is as follows:

5.5.1. Isolated footing:

The design procedure of isolated footing is as follows:

1. The factored load is obtained from ETABS20.0.0 analysis and other moment features in x and y direction.
2. Area of footing is obtained by =total service load /Safe bearing capacity of soil

$$\text{Load (P)} = \text{Service load} + \text{Self weight of footing}$$

Type of footing is selected i.e. either square or rectangle and length and breadth is determined.

3. Upward earth pressure acting on footing is determined by =

$$\frac{\text{Total factored load}}{\text{area}} \pm \frac{M_x}{l_x} \pm \frac{M_y}{l_y} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

4. Eccentricity on footing due to acting moment is determined in x and y-direction = M/P (factored load)
5. Maximum occurring bending moment in the footing is calculated according to the clause 34.2.3.1 and 34.2.3.2 of IS code 456:2000.

6. Depth of footing is calculated by

$$M_u = 0.133 * f_{ck} * b * d^2 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

And depth is increased 2-3 times to resist shear.

7. Reinforcement is calculated using

$$M_u = 0.87 f_y A_{st} * d (1 - A_{st} f_y / b * d * f_{ck}) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

and spacing of the bars is also determined.

8. One-way shear is checked according to Cl 34.2.4.1 of IS code 456-2000 and with the help of Cl 40.1 of IS code 456-2000.
9. Two-way shear is also checked by using CL 31.6.2.1 of is code and Cl 31.6.3.1 also helps it.
10. Development length required is obtained and checked $L_d = \sigma_s * \phi / (4Tbd)$ with the help of IS 456:2000 Cl 26.2.1.1 page12.
11. Development length available is obtained by =

$$\frac{L}{2} - \frac{l}{2} - ex - cover \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

12. Development length is checked for safety and bends accordingly upward 90°.

5.5.2 Combined footing:

The design procedure of combined footing is as follows.

1. The factored load is obtained from ETABS 17.0.0 analysis and other moment features in x and y direction.

2. Locate the point of application of column loads on the footing.
3. Proportion the footing such that resultant of loads passes through the center of footing.
4. Compute the area of footing such that the allowable soil pressure is not exceeded.
5. Determine factored upward pressure.
6. Calculate the shear force and bending moment at the silent point and hence draw shear force diagram (SFD) and bending moment diagram (BMD).
7. Fix the depth of footing from the maximum bending moment

$$\mu = 0.133 * f_{ck} * b * d^2 \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

And depth is increased 2-3 times to resist shear.

8. Calculate the transverse bending moment and design the transverse section for depth and reinforcement.
9. Check depth of footing for one-way shear **CL 34.2.4.1 of IS 456-2000** and with the help of **CL 40.1 of IS 456-2000**.
10. Check for two-way shear using **CL 31.6.2.1** and **CL 31.6.3.1 of IS 456- 2000**.
11. Design the reinforcement for the longitudinal moment and place them in the appropriate positions.
12. Draw and detail the reinforcement.

Chapter 6

STRUCTURAL LOADING

6.1 Project Description

The site of the project is selected on Bharatpur-11, Chitwan where our proposed building is designed as a multi-storey residential building. The salient features of our project are as follows:

Name of the project	: Structural analysis and design of earthquake resistant 4 storey apartment building at Bharatpur
Location	: Region: Central Development Region
Province	: 2
Zone	: Bagmati
District	: Chitwan
Building Type	: Multi-storied Apartment Building
Structural System	: Standard Moment Resisting Frame
Seismic zone	: V
Plot area	: 2000 m ²
Number of storey	: 4 (G + 3 storey)
Dimension of Building	: Maximum length: 16.963m
Maximum breadth	: 6.654m
Type of stair	: Open-well
Height of Building	: 21.336m
Floor height	: 3.048m
Types of column	: Square
Types of beam	: Rectangle
Design criteria	: As per IS code
No of columns	: 15
Bearing capacity of soil (σ)	: 150 KN/m ²

A. Dead Load Identification

1	Unit weight of material		
	Reinforced concrete	=	24 KN/m ³
	Brick masonry	=	19.6 KN/m ³
	Screed	=	22 KN/m ³
	Cement plaster	=	20.4 KN/m ³
	Marble	=	26.5 KN/m ³
2	Thickness allowed		
	Thickness of structural slab	=	0.130 m
	Thickness of screed	=	0.025 m
	Thickness of ceiling plaster	=	0.0125 m
	Thickness of marble	=	0.025 m
3	Height of Beam, wall & parapet walls		
	Depth of beam	=	0.350 m
	Height of story of building	=	3.048 m
	Height of parapet wall	=	1 m

B. Live load calculation

Live load in bed room and living room	=	2	KN/m ²
Live load in corridor, staircase, balconies	=	3	KN/m ²
Roof live loads (accessible)	=	1.5	KN/m ²
Roof live loads (Inaccessible)	=	0.75	KN/m ²

6.2 Lateral Load

Lateral loads, primarily wind and earthquake loads, are significant factors in the design of structures. While both types of loads can affect a building, the probability of them occurring simultaneously is low. For the proposed residential building in Bharatpur, a region more prone to earthquakes than wind, the design focuses on earthquake loads.

Accordingly, the structural design is governed by the provisions of IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016, which outlines the criteria for earthquake-resistant design of structures. Considering the seismic vulnerability of the area, the wind load has been deemed less critical, and the building's design is optimized for seismic forces.

6.3 Base Shear:

Base shear is the total lateral force that occurs at structure base due to earthquake.

According to **IS 1893 (part I): 2016 CL.NO.6.4.2** the design horizontal seismic coefficient A_h for a structure shall be determined by the following expression:

$$A_h = \frac{ZIS_a}{2Rg}$$

Where, Z = Zone factor given by **IS 1893 (Part I): 2016 Table 3 (cl 6.4.2)**

I = Importance factor, 1.0 for residential building **table 8 (cl.7.2.3)**

R = Response reduction factor given by **IS 1893 (Part I): 2016 Table 9 (cl 7.2.6)**

$\frac{s_a}{g}$ = Average response acceleration coefficient which depends on Fundamental natural period of vibration (T_a).

$$T_a = 0.075h^{0.75}$$

Where, h = height of the building

According to **IS 1893 (Part I): 2016 CL.NO 7.2.1** the total design lateral force or design seismic base shear V_B along any principle direction is given by:

$$V_B = A_h * W_i$$

Where, W_i = Seismic weight of a floor i^{th}

Table 1: Seismic weight of building and base shear calculation

Loads\On due to (KN)	GF	1st floor	2nd floor	Roof
1. Slab		390.9018	390.9018	770.269
2. Column		140.0175	140.0175	37.338
3. Beam		338.969	338.969	142.907
4. Walls		660.008	660.008	191.45
5. Staircase		304.729	304.729	
Total		1834.6253	1834.6253	1141.964

Z	0.36	(Table-3)
I	1	(cl 7.2.3 p-19)
R	5	(Table -19)

$T_a = 0.075h^{0.75}$	
h	12.192
T _a	0.489348
s _a /g	2.5
A _h	0.09
W	4811.21
V _B	433.0089

Chapter 7

STRUCTURAL MODELLING AND ANALYSIS

7.1 Modeling:

Generally, modeling is the art or activity of making three-dimensional models. In term of building, it represents 3D modeling of buildings structure. Before finalize the building construction at site it helps to visualize the structure. For modeling of structure, we used ETABS17.0.0 which is both modeling as well as analyzing tool.

Figure 4: ETABS modelling of Proposed Building

7.2 Working procedure of ETABS 20.0

Step-1: Initial setup of Standard Codes and Country codes

Step-2: Creation of Grid points:

After getting opened with ETABS new model was selected and the grid dimensions were entered

Step-3: Defining property:

Here, the material property was defined by selecting define menu material properties. New material for our structural components (beams, columns, slabs) was added by giving the specified details in the definition. After that defined the section size by selecting frame sections & added the required section for beams, columns, etc.

Step-4: Assigning of property:

After defining the property, drew the structural components using command menu. Drew line for beam for beams and create columns in region for columns by which property assigning was completed for beams and columns.

Step-5: Assigning of supports:

By keeping the selection at the base of the structure and selecting all the columns and assigned supports by going to assign menu joint/frame Restraints (supports) fixed.

Step-6: Defining of loads

In ETABS 20.0.0, all the load considerations were first defined and then assigned. The loads in ETABS were defined as using static load cases command in define menu.

Step-7: Assigning of Dead Loads:

After defining all the loads. Dead loads were automatically assigned in ETABS i.e., inbuilt.

Step-8: Assigning of Live Loads:

Live load was assigned for the entire structure including floor finishing.

Step-9: Assigning of load combination:

Using load combinations command in define menu appropriate combinations of load was considered as per **IS 1893 (Part I) : 2016**.

Step-10: Analysis:

After the completion of all the above procedure, analysis and checked for errors. The following analysis were carried out for various topics such as:

- Load considerations
- Base Shear Reaction
- Equivalent lateral load distribution of load on each inter-storey
- Inter story drift
- Modal Participation Mass Ratios
- Base Reaction
- Design of each structural elements like Slab, Beam, Column, Stair-case, footings.

Step-11: Design: And based on this, further design was carried out of structural components.

7.3 Materials adopted in our design

Concrete Grade=**M25** (1:1 1/2:3)

Rebar grade=Fe 500 and Fe 415

Use of **IS 456-2000, IS 1893-2016, IS 13920-2016**

➤ **7.4 Defined elements:**

7.4.1 Section defined:

Main Beam: **230mm × 350mm**

Column: **350 mm × 350 mm**

Slab: 125 mm

7.4.2.Load combination:

Load combinations are the independent loadings formed by the linear combination of the independent loading conditions. The different load cases have combined as per **IS 1893 part-I (cl 6.3.1)**

The wind load is not considered as a principal load case for the building as the earthquake load plays a dominant role in the formation of load combinations.

The basic load in combinations for design consideration are :

- 1) $0.9DL-1.5EQX$
- 2) $0.9DL-1.5EQY$
- 3) $0.9DL+1.5EQX$
- 4) $0.9DL+1.5EQY$
- 5) $1.2(DL+LL+EQX)$
- 6) $1.2(DL+LL+EQY)$
- 7) $1.2(DL+LL-EQX)$
- 8) $1.2(DL+LL-EQY)$
- 9) $1.5(DL+EQX)$
- 10) $1.5(DL+EQY)$
- 11) $1.5(DL+LL)$
- 12) $1.5(DL-EQX)$
- 13) $1.5(DL-EQY)$
- 14) $1.5DL$

Where,

LL= live load

DL=Dead load

EQ_x=Earthquake load along x-direction

EQ_y=Earthquake load along y-direction

EQ=Earthquake load

(Bureau of Indian Standards New Delhi, 2016

7.4.3 Load patterns defined:

Load patterns refers to the distribution and variation of load of structure. It include dead loads, wind loads, earthquake loads, etc. Load patterns allow us to define and manage load pattern in ETABS efficiently. It defines the patterns of various loads which has different type, multiplier and lateral load. Among them self-weight multiplier for dead load is taken as **1** because ETABS software calculate load itself. But for other load we need to assign load manually as per design requirement, so we consider self-weight multiplier as **0** other than dead load.

Table 2:load patterns

Load	Type	Self wt. Multiplier	Auto Lateral load
Dead	Dead	1	
Live	Live	0	
Water tank load	Super Dead	0	
Wall load	Super Dead	0	
Staircase loads	Super Dead	0	
EQx	Seismic	0	IS 1893:2016
EQy	Seismic	0	IS 1893:2016
Floor finish	Super dead	0	

➤ 7.4.4 Diaphragm defined:

A diaphragm in building construction refers to a structural element, typically a horizontal plane, that help to distribute lateral forces (such as those from wind or seismic activity) to the vertical resisting elements of the structure, like shear walls or frames. Diaphragms play a crucial role in maintaining the stability and integrity of a building these during these events.

Figure 5: Diaphragm of building

Table 3: diaphragm defined

Name	Rigidity Type
D1	Rigid
D2	Rigid
D3	Rigid
D4	Rigid

7.4.5 Mass Source defined

In structural analysis, particularly for earthquake-resistant design, accurately defining the mass source is essential for determining the seismic forces that building may face. In ETABS and similar structural software, the mass source defines how the building's mass is allocated and utilized in dynamic analysis to produce seismic loads. The dead load multiplier is taken as 1 because the dead loads are considered to be constant i.e. 100% and live load is less than 3KN/m² so 25% of live load provided due to variable load which is not fully loaded all times. In case of live load is greater than 3KN/m² 50% of live load is taken.

Table 4:mass source diagram

Name	Load Pattern	Multiplier
MsSrc1	Dead	1
MsSrc1	Live	0.25
MsSrc1	Floor finish	1
MsSrc1	Wall load	1
MsSrc1	Staircase steps	1
MsSrc1	Water tank load	1

7.4.6 3D view of load assigned:

Figure Illustrates the wall loads which are shown in below table.

Figure 6: wall load

Table 5:load assigned

SN	Description	Load (KN/M)
1	Parapet	2.489
2	Staircase load	1.879
3	Floor finish	1.5

Chapter 8

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

8.1 Forces in Structural Analysis:

8.1.1 Shear force Diagram:

Maximum shear force occurs at support. The red sign indicates negative shear force which is downward similarly yellow indicate positive upward shear force. 1.5DL+1.5LL load combination prefer for shear force diagram of structure.

Figure 7: Shear force diagram

8.1.2 Axial force Diagram

Axial force lies along length of structural member such as column and wall. Axial force is maximum at base and gradually decrease with increase in height. 1.5(DL+LL) load combination prefer for axial force diagram of structure.

Figure 9: Bending moment diagram

8.1.4 Eccentricity calculation

According to NBC 105: 2020, for the analysis for the torsional effects, the applied torsion at each level shall use either the forces calculated by the Equivalent static method or the combined story inertial forces found in a model Response spectrum method. The accidental eccentricity can be taken as ± 10 .

Table 6: Centre of Rigidity and Centre of stiffness

Ultimate Limit State								
Storey	XCCM	YCCM	XCR	YCR	ex	ey	% X	% Y
	m	m	m	m	m	m		
1st floor	8.3648	3.3714	8.309	4.2206	0.0558	0.8465	0.33%	12.72%
2nd floor	8.5318	3.3352	8.1715	4.3973	0.3603	1.0621	2.16%	15.96%
3rd floor	8.0304	3.6865	8.1463	4.4687	0.1159	0.7822	0.69%	11.76%
4th floor	6.604	4.9682	6.9912	4.8152	0.3872	0.153	2.32%	2.30%

8.1.5 Story Drift check

Storey Drift is the relative displacement between floors above and/or below the storey under consideration. As per Indian standard, Criteria for earthquake resistant design of structures, IS 1893(Part 1):2002, the storey drift in any story shall not exceed 0.004 times the height of storey.

8.1.6 Story Displacement Check

Storey displacement is the deflection of a single story relative to the base or ground level of the structure.

As per IS 1893(Part 1):2002, the storey drift in any storey due to the minimum specified design lateral force, with partial load factor of 1.0 shall not exceed 0.004 times the storey height.

Table 7: Inter storey drift

1 For EQX

Story	Displacement	Design Displacement	Drift	Floor Height	Drift Ratio	Check
	mm	mm	mm	mm		<0.004
4	17.299	17.299	5.282	3000	0.0017607	OK
3	12.017	12.017	3.572	3000	0.0011907	OK
2	8.445	8.445	4.865	3000	0.0016217	OK
1	3.58	3.58	3.58	3000	0.0011933	OK
Base	0	0				

2 For EQY

Story	Displacement	Design Displacement	Drift	Floor Height	Drift Ratio	Check
	mm	mm	mm	mm		<0.004
4	18.444	18.444	3.717	3000	0.001239	OK
3	14.727	14.727	4.078	3000	0.0013593	OK
2	10.649	10.649	6.096	3000	0.002032	OK
1	4.553	4.553	4.553	3000	0.0015177	OK
Base	0	0				

8.1.7 Soft storey check

Soft story is the one whose stiffness of the lateral-force-resisting system is less than 70% of the lateral-force-resisting system stiffness in an adjacent story above or below, or less than 80% of the average lateral-force-resisting system stiffness of the three stories above or below.

Table 8: soft storey check

Storey Stiffness								
	Load Case	Stiffness	Check		Load Case	Stiffness	Check	
Floor	Load	kN/m	70% of K(i+1)	80% of K(i+n)/2		kN/m	70% of K(i+1)	80% of K(i+n)/2
6th Floor	EQx		-	-	EQy		-	-
5th Floor	EQx		OK	-	EQy		OK	-
4th floor	EQx	11458.81	OK	-	EQy	12168.89	OK	-
3rd Floor	EQx	67613.76	OK	OK	EQy	47330.89	OK	OK
2nd Floor	EQx	95790.13	OK	OK	EQy	64888.57	OK	OK
1st Floor	EQx	129332.6	OK	OK	EQy	89013.92	OK	OK

Serviceability Limit State								
Storey Stiffness								
	Load Case	Stiffness	Check		Load Case	Stiffness	Check	
Floor	Load	kN/m	70% of K(i+1)	80% of K(i+n)/2		kN/m	70% of K(i+1)	80% of K(i+n)/2
6th Floor	EQx		-	-	EQy		-	-
5th Floor	EQx		OK	-	EQy		OK	-

4th floor	EQx	11458.8 1	OK	-	EQy	12168.8 9	OK	-
3rd Floor	EQx	67613.7 6	OK	OK	EQy	47330.8 9	OK	OK
2nd Floor	EQx	95790.1 3	OK	OK	EQy	64888.5 7	OK	OK
1st Floor	EQx	129332. 6	OK	OK	EQy	89013.9 2	OK	OK

8.2 Joint reactions

Joint reactions refer to the forces and moments that develop at the connections or joints between structural elements, such as beams, columns and slabs. Below figure shows the Joint reaction, where the base reaction consist of forces, moments where FX,FY and FZ indicates the forces in respective direction X,Y and Z. MX, MY and MZ indicates the forces action along X,Y and Z direction respectively.

Table 9: joint reaction

TABLE: Joint Reactions										
Story	Label	Unique Name	Output Case	Case Type	FX	FY	FZ	MX	MY	MZ
					kN	kN	kN	kN-m	kN-m	kN-m
Base	A1	53	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	4.8934	4.5383	396.7818	-2.4766	2.7126	0.1604
Base	A2	54	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	4.5469	-2.8817	626.3277	4.962	2.017	0.1604
Base	A3	55	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	4.1923	-9.3136	382.9372	11.4099	1.3133	0.1604
Base	B1	56	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	2.4514	8.4167	552.3136	-6.8086	0.2645	0.1604
Base	B2	57	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	0.8539	-2.565	915.3171	4.2005	-1.6852	0.1604
Base	B3	58	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	24.0682	-51.5669	609.7837	29.8935	6.2189	-0.2298
Base	C1	59	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-7.8387	5.9954	449.6836	-4.8756	-10.0513	0.1604
Base	C2	60	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-9.1195	-2.8064	827.0594	3.9481	-11.6834	0.1604
Base	C3	61	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-26.374	-20.6405	608.1353	19.9904	-26.6467	-0.1703
Base	D1	62	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-1.0195	6.6963	449.4816	-5.9611	-3.215	0.1604
Base	D2	63	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-1.7847	-0.8728	644.078	1.6269	-4.3303	0.1604
Base	D3	64	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-2.1179	-7.8609	457.6423	8.6324	-5.0126	0.1604
Base	E1	65	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-6.5189	6.0847	395.1353	-5.776	-8.7281	0.1604
Base	E2	66	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-6.0893	0.0654	597.6622	0.2584	-8.6458	0.1604
Base	E3	67	1.5(DL+LL)	Combination	-7.2897	-6.4115	393.8485	6.7514	-10.1974	0.1604

8.3 Stiffness/ Rigidity irregularities

As per IS 1893(Part 1):2016, Center Stiffness irregularity is present in the structure when the lateral stiffness of a story is less than that of the story above. This irregularity is also known as a soft story. Soft stories are more prone to collapse or deform under lateral loads.

In an earthquake, a soft story can fail catastrophically, leading to the collapse of the entire building.

8.3 Modal Mass Participation:

Modal participation mass ratio indicates the percentage of structural mass of the model participating in a given direction and model. According to IS 1893(Part 1):2016, a lateral story regular building should contribute at least 65% of mass in each direction.

Table 10: modal participating mass ratios

TABLE: Modal Participating Mass Ratios														
Case	Mode	Period	UX	UY	UZ	SumUX	SumUY	SumUZ	RX	RY	RZ	SumRX	SumRY	SumRZ
		sec												
Modal	1	0.663	0.143	0.0031	0	0.143	0.0031	0	0.005	0.0201	0.7143	0.005	0.0201	0.7143
Modal	2	0.648	0.0038	0.8448	0	0.1468	0.8479	0	0.18	0.0006	0.0016	0.1851	0.0206	0.716
Modal	3	0.522	0.6916	0.002	0	0.8384	0.8499	0	0.0001	0.178	0.1444	0.1851	0.1987	0.8604
Modal	4	0.252	0.0001	0.0773	0	0.8385	0.9273	0	0.5419	0.0001	0.0087	0.7271	0.1987	0.8691
Modal	5	0.247	0.0697	0.00001397	0	0.9081	0.9273	0	0	0.3912	0.0001	0.7271	0.59	0.8692
Modal	6	0.213	0.0032	0.007	0	0.9113	0.9343	0	0.0471	0.0145	0.0863	0.7741	0.6045	0.9555
Modal	7	0.175	0.0001	0.0466	0	0.9113	0.9809	0	0.1812	0.0003	0.0001	0.9554	0.6048	0.9555
Modal	8	0.169	0.0196	0.0021	0	0.9309	0.983	0	0.0093	0.0993	0.004	0.9646	0.704	0.9595
Modal	9	0.155	0.051	0.0003	0	0.9819	0.9833	0	0.0009	0.2634	0.0147	0.9655	0.9675	0.9742
Modal	10	0.128	0.0033	0.0029	0	0.9852	0.9862	0	0.0055	0.0056	0.0206	0.971	0.9731	0.9949
Modal	11	0.125	0.0006	0.0138	0	0.9858	1	0	0.029	0.0012	0.0014	1	0.9743	0.9963
Modal	12	0.108	0.0142	0.00001769	0	1	1	0	0.00001241	0.0257	0.0037	1	1	1

8.4 Beam/Column & Column/Beam Capacity Ratios

The beam/column and column/beam capacity are important concepts in structural engineering, particularly in the context of earthquake-resistant design. At each beam-column joint of moment-resisting frame, the sum of nominal design strength of columns meeting at that joint (with nominal strength calculated for the factored axial load in the direction of the lateral force under consideration so as to give least column nominal design strength) along each principal plane shall be at least 1.4 times the sum of nominal design strength of beams meeting at that joint in the same plane. **(IS 13920: 2016).**

Figure 10:beam\column capacity ratio

Figure 11: column/beam capacity ratio

The figure shows the Column Beam Capacity Ratio are greater than 1.4 whereas Beam Column Ratio are less than 1.

8.5 Equivalent Lateral Load:

Equivalent Lateral Loads (ELL) are simplified representations of the lateral forces acting on a structure due to seismic activity. These loads are used in the design and analysis of building, particularly in regions prone to earthquakes, to ensure that structures can with

stand seismic forces. The equivalent lateral load method is a simplified seismic analysis procedure that converts the complex dynamic effects of an earth into a set of static forces applied to the structures.

Figure 12: equivalent lateral load EQY

Figure 13: equivalent lateral load EQX

8.6 Center of Mass and Rigidity:

Center of mass is the point through which the earthquake loads act through the building. And the point through which a horizontal force is applied resultant in translation of flow without any rotation is called center of rigidity. Unless otherwise state, the inertia force considered is that associated with the horizontal shaking of the building. **(IS 1893(Part1):2016, clause 4.4).**

Table11:centers of mass and rigidity

TABLE: Centers Of Mass And Rigidity											
Story	Diaphragm	Mass X	Mass Y	XCM	YCM	Cum Mass X	Cum Mass Y	XCCM	YCCM	XCR	YCR
		kg	kg	m	m	kg	kg	m	m	m	m
Story1	D1	186394.43	186394.43	8.3252	3.362	186394.43	186394.43	8.3252	3.362	8.3064	4.2215
Story2	D2	124635.16	124635.16	8.4766	3.3213	124635.16	124635.16	8.4766	3.3213	8.1687	4.3945
Story3	D3	52875.63	52875.63	8.0121	3.6635	52875.63	52875.63	8.0121	3.6635	8.1422	4.4652
Story4	D4	9648.18	9648.18	6.604	4.9682	9648.18	9648.18	6.604	4.9682	6.9903	4.8149

8.7 TORSIONAL IRREGULARITY CALCULATION

According to IS 1893(Part 1):2002, Torsion irregularity is to be considered to exist when the maximum storey drift, computed with design eccentricity, at one end of the structure transverse to an axis is more than 1.2 times the average of the storey drifts at the two end of the structure.

Figure 14: Torsional Irregularity

Table 12: torsional irregularity calculations

Story	Load Case/Combo	Direction	Maximum	Average	Minimum	Ratio	Check
			mm	mm	mm		
Story4	EQX	X	17.19	16.892	16.594	1.02	OK
Story3	EQX	X	12.018	11.44	10.862	1.05	OK
Story2	EQX	X	8.446	8.019	7.592	1.05	OK
Story1	EQX	X	3.586	3.425	3.264	1.05	OK
Story4	EQY	Y	18.377	18.118	17.859	1.01	OK
Story3	EQY	Y	14.615	13.757	12.899	1.06	OK
Story2	EQY	Y	10.542	9.718	8.894	1.08	OK
Story1	EQY	Y	4.511	4.18	3.849	1.08	OK

8.8 Mass Irregularity

As per IS 1893(Part 1):2016, a structure is considered to possess center of mass irregularities if the seismic weight of any floor is more than 150% of the seismic weight of the floor below. Mass irregularity can lead to structural instability, making buildings more vulnerable to damage from earthquakes, wind loads, and other environmental factors. Irregularities can create areas of high stress, causing the building to fail or collapse during extreme events.

Table 13:mass irregularity

Mass Irregularity		
Floor	Mass	Check
	Kg	50% EL(i±1)
4	20523.49	-
3	106949.7	OK
2	182003.2	OK
1	192450.4	-

Chapter 9

DETAIL STRUCTURAL DESIGN AND DRAWING

After completion of preliminary design, the structure is analyzed for different load cases and combinations. The results from this analysis can then be used to redesign the sections based on more accurate information on the effects of different types of loads acting on the structure. These sections are iteratively redesigned such that they meet different response criteria set up by codal provisions as well as from professional experiences.

9.1 ETABS Reinforcement output:

Figure below shows the longitudinal reinforcement of different Storey.

Figure 15: plan

Figure 16:elevation

9.2 Design summary:

After analyzing the given structure using the software ETABS17.0.0, the structural elements are designed manually as well as by ETABS which is shown in ANNEXES. Design summary of each element is shown in following tables:

9.2.1 Design summary of slab: (one long edge discontinuous):

Table 14: design summary of slab

Panel	Types of Slabs	Reinforcement	
		Longer span	Shorter span
All	One long edge discontinuous	8mm ϕ @150 c/c	8mm ϕ @150 c/c

9.2.2 Design Summary of beam:

The reinforcement data acquired from ETABS is utilized to create design summaries for beams. Following table shows the design summary of critical beam of first floor. The manual beam design details are shown in **Annex**.

Table 15: Design summary of beam

member	Section Position	Steel Reinforcement position	Area Required A_r (mm ²)	Bars	Area
				Provided	Provided A_p (mm ²)
B1-C1	Left-end	Top	678.579	3-16Ø+2-12Ø	829.382
		Bottom	339.290	2-16Ø+1-12Ø	515.222
	Mid-span	Top	116.562	3-16Ø	603.187
		Bottom	233.125	2-16Ø+1-12Ø	515.222
	Right-end	Top	678.579	3-16Ø+2-12Ø	829.392
		Bottom	306.146	2-16Ø+1-12Ø	515.222

9.2.3 Design Summary of Secondary beam:

The reinforcement data acquired from ETABS is utilized to create design summaries for beams. Following table shows the design summary of secondary beam of first floor. The manual beam design details are shown in **Annex**.

Table 16:design summary of secondary beam

Member	Section Position	Steel Reinforcement position	Area Required A_r (mm ²)	Bars Provided	Area Provided A_p (mm ²)
50	Left-end	Top	209.914	2-16 Φ	402.124
		Bottom	217.431	2-16 Φ	402.124
	Mid-span	Top	217.431	2-16 Φ	402.124
		Bottom	217.431	2-16 Φ	402.124
	Right-end	Top	217.431	2-16 Φ	402.124
		Bottom	171.347	2-16 Φ	402.124

9.2.4 Design Summary of column:

The reinforcement data acquired from ETABS is utilized to create design summaries for beams.

Following table shows the design summary of columns in first floor.

Table 17:design summary of column

Column	Size	Nos	Floor	Reinforcement	Etabs Result
C1	14"x14"	10	Ground	8-16 Ø	8-16 Ø
	14"x14"	10	First	8-16 Ø	8-16 Ø
	14"x14"	10	Second	8-16 Ø	8-16 Ø
	14"x14"	2	Stair cover	8-16 Ø	8-16 Ø
C2	14"x14"	1	Ground	4-20 Ø + 4-16 Ø	4-20 Ø + 4-16 Ø
	14"x14"	1	First		
	14"x14"	1	Second	8-16 Ø	8-16 Ø
	14"x14"	1	Stair cover	8-16 Ø	8-16 Ø
C3	14"x14"	1	Ground	4-25 Ø + 4-20 Ø	4-25 Ø + 4-20 Ø
	14"x14"	1	First	8-20 Ø	8-20 Ø
	14"x14"	1	Second	4-20 Ø + 4-16 Ø	4-20 Ø + 4-16 Ø
	14"x14"	1	Stair cover	8-16 Ø	8-16 Ø
C4	14"x14"	3	Ground	4-16 Ø + 4-12 Ø	4-16 Ø + 4-12 Ø
	14"x14"	3	First	4-16 Ø + 4-12 Ø	4-16 Ø + 4-12 Ø
	14"x14"	3	Second	4-16 Ø + 4-12 Ø	4-16 Ø + 4-12 Ø

9.2.5 Design Summary of Staircase:

The manually design of staircase is shown in Annex 1. Following table shows design summary of staircase.

Table 18: Design Summary of staircase

Overall Depth	150mm
Waist Slab Overall Depth	150mm
Reinforcement Bar	12 mm@150mmc/c spacing
Distribution Bar	8 mm@200mmc/c spacing

9.2.6 Design Summary of Footing:

Table 19: design summary of footing

Footing	Grid	length	Breadth	Rebar
SF1	1A,2A,3A	1.8m	1.8m	12mm ϕ @150 c/c
SF2	1D,2D,3D	1.8m	1.8m	12mm ϕ @150 c/c
SF3	1E,2E,3E	1.8m	1.8m	12mm ϕ @150 c/c
CF1	1B,2B,3B	5m	2.55m	12mm ϕ @100 c/c
CF2	1C,2C,3C	5m	2.55m	12mm ϕ @100 c/c

Conclusion

The structural analysis and design of the earthquake-resistant four-storey apartment building presented in this project has been carried out in accordance with established engineering principles, relevant design codes, and seismic safety requirements. The study primarily focused on achieving a safe, stable, economical, and serviceable structural system capable of withstanding both gravity loads and seismic forces expected in earthquake-prone regions.

Preliminary planning and sizing of structural elements such as beams, columns, slabs, and foundations were performed based on standard design assumptions and codal provisions. These preliminary calculations played a crucial role in developing an efficient structural layout and ensuring compatibility between architectural and structural requirements. The appropriate grades of concrete and reinforcing steel were selected to satisfy strength, durability, and ductility requirements, thereby ensuring the building's ability to perform satisfactorily under both normal and extreme loading conditions.

A comprehensive structural analysis was conducted using ETABS software, which enabled accurate modeling of the building geometry, material properties, and boundary conditions. Various load cases including dead load, live load, and seismic load were defined, and suitable load combinations were applied as per seismic design codes. The use of ETABS significantly improved the accuracy and efficiency of analysis, allowing detailed evaluation of internal forces, displacements, storey drift, and overall structural behavior under earthquake loading.

Special emphasis was placed on seismic design considerations such as ductile detailing, load path continuity, and lateral force-resisting mechanisms. The building was analyzed for different earthquake parameters, taking into account seismic zone factors, soil conditions, importance factors, and response reduction factors. The results demonstrated that the structure satisfies the permissible limits for storey drift, displacement, and member forces, thereby ensuring adequate seismic performance and occupant safety during earthquake events.

The design of individual structural components was carried out to meet strength and serviceability criteria while complying with ductile detailing provisions. Proper reinforcement detailing was ensured to enhance energy dissipation capacity and prevent brittle failure during seismic excitation. The overall structural system was designed to

exhibit controlled and predictable behavior, minimizing the risk of collapse and reducing potential damage during strong ground motion.

Beyond technical aspects, this project significantly enhanced practical engineering skills, including interpretation of design codes, application of software tools, and integration of theoretical knowledge with real-world structural problems. The project also fostered teamwork, coordination, and effective communication among group members and supervisors, which are essential qualities in professional engineering practice.

In conclusion, this project successfully demonstrates a systematic approach to the structural analysis and design of an earthquake-resistant residential building. The knowledge and experience gained through this study provide a strong foundation for future professional work in structural and seismic engineering. The methodologies and conclusions derived from this project can serve as a reference for similar low-rise residential buildings in seismic regions, contributing to safer and more resilient infrastructure development.

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Annex A:

